

Working with folders in the JAVA programming language

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ANNOTATION

This article looks at classes and class-related issues, including folders, in the JAVA programming language. Also, solutions to these problems are provided

Keywords : package , classpath, Friendly

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All the identifiers we've used in our examples so far are in the same place in the names. (namespace). This meant that we had to worry about each class having its own unique name to avoid problems. Folders are a mechanism for working with namespaces and limiting visibility. Each extension JAVA file has 4 identical internals, of which we have used only one in our examples so far. Below is the initial form of the JAVA file.

1. Package single operator (optional)
2. Import any number of operators (optional)
3. Public class single announcement.
4. (private) folder any number of private classes (optional).
5. Package operator. The first thing that appears in a JAVA initialization file

is the package operator, which tells the compiler in which folder the classes in this file should be defined. Packages. Folders provide a separate collection of names where class names are stored. If the package operator is not specified, the classes fall into the unsigned namespace of silent names. If you declare a class as belonging to a specific folder, e.g.

Package java. out image; then the initialization code of this class must be stored in the java / awt / image directory.

The directory that the JAVA compiler treats as the root of the folder hierarchy can be specified using the CLASSPATH environment variable. This variable can be used to specify multiple root directories for a folder hierarchy.

Import operator. After the Package operator, but before any classes are defined in the initial JAVA file, there may be a list of import operators. Folders are a good mechanism for keeping classes separate, so all classes implemented in JAVA are stored in folders. The general form of the import operator is as follows:

Import volume 1 [. volume 2]. (classname / *),

Here, folder 1 is the name of the top level folder, folder 2 is the folder name of the folder inside the first folder and not necessarily separated by a dot. And, therefore, after the path in the folder hierarchy, either the class name or the metacharacter "*" (asterisk) is displayed. The asterisk indicates that if the JAVA translator needs a class for which a folder is not specified, it should look at the contents of the asterisked folder instead of the class name. The code snippet below shows both forms of the import operator:

Import java. wtil . Date

Import java. io. *

JAVA Access Specifiers.

- public : path to the interface.

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- «friendly» (Dustana).
- private : the path is forbidden.
- protected : path for subclasses.

JAVA path specification public, protected and private class precedes every definition of its members, whether they are information, structure, or style. Each routing specifier controls the routing of the member definition it precedes.

public : open a path to the interface.

When a path of type public is used, it means that the member following the word public is open to everyone. Any class can access classes defined as public from any folder.

Public typecasting can be used for data objects, as long as it does not cause unwanted inconvenience when using it outside the class.

```
public int a;
```

"Friendly" (Friendly).

No specifier is defined before this or that class member

If so, when it (a member of this class) is silent, it opens a path without a keyword. This way opening is understood as friendly dek (friendly). This means that all other classes in the current folder have access to this class member. But for classes outside the folder, the path to this member of the class is closed. Friendly type routing allows you to group related classes within a folder.

Let's use the definitions of public and friendly as an example.

```
package food. desserts;  
public class Cookie {  
    public Cookie () {  
        system. out. println("Cookie constructor");  
    }  
    void decorate () { system . out. println ("Cookie decorated"); }  
}
```

To a separate file:

```
// import food dessert * ;  
public class Dinner {  
    public static void main (string args [ ]) {  
        Cookie C = new Cookie ( );  
        // !c. decorate ( ); // freight  
    }  
}
```

private : the path is denied.

The private keyword tells these members that no one outside of that class's methods has access. Other classes in that folder have no access to members defined as private, which is the most restricted access level.

Information finders defined as private are only accessible to the class they belong to. This type of path is used: for variables that make the object wild when referenced outside the class;

methods that expose the object when invoked at run time outside the class;

```
class Resource {
```

```
private static count = 5;  
private Resource ( ) { }  
static Resource make A Resource ( ) {  
if (count > 0) { count - -; return new Resource
```

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